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Article

Community-Driven Risk Assessment: Integrating Local Perceptions into Quantifiable Risk Weights Using Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)-Geographical Information System (GIS)

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ABSTRACT

This study integrates the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Geographic Information System (GIS) to assess community flood risk in Maidipur, Kurigram, Bangladesh an area frequently affected by monsoon flooding. By combining community-based hazard and vulnerability indicators and satellite-derived hydrological, meteorological, and geological data, the research develops a Community Risk Map to identify and categorize hazard-prone zones. Fourteen indicators were ranked and weighted using AHP to generate hazard and vulnerability indices, which were then spatially overlaid in GIS to produce a composite flood risk map. Network also applied to identify optimal evacuation routes and assembly points based on shortest time travel and distance, avoid risk zone. Traditionally, practitioners relied on community perception and a limited set of factors for risk mapping. This study advances that approach by aligning local knowledge with scientific analysis, achieving a high accuracy rate (96.88%) validated through field visits and community engagement... The findings offer evidence-based insights for flood preparedness, shelter placement, and community resilience planning under the Disaster Risk Management framework.

KEYWORDS

Analytical hierarchy process (AHP); community risk mapping; hazard index and vulnerability index; remote sensing; transect walk; historical timeline; seasonal calendar; focus group discussion (FGD); key informant interview (KII); participatory rural appraisal (PRA) and geographic information system (GIS).

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1. Introduction

Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) has been widely used to develop community risk maps, capturing valuable local perceptions of hazards and vulnerabilities (Chambers, 1994; Mercer et al., 2009). However, PRA-based approaches often rely heavily on subjective judgments, which may not fully represent the actual extent or severity of risks. Such limitations can lead to inaccuracies in identifying priority areas, evacuation routes, and mitigation measures, reducing the effectiveness of preparedness and resilience strategies.

To address this gap, there is a need to integrate participatory approaches with fact-based analytical techniques. Combining the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) offers a robust framework for enhancing the objectivity and precision of community risk mapping. AHP supports systematic prioritization of risk factors by assigning relative weights (Saaty, 1987; Abdel Rahman Al-Shabeeb, 2016; Daniela Rincon, 2018), while GIS enables spatial analysis and visualization of hazard and vulnerability data (Generino P. Siddayao, 2014; Kabir Uddin, 2021). Together, these methods can transform community insights into quantifiable, evidence-based risk assessments.

Recent studies on flood risk mapping have applied the GIS based AHP and MVDM approach to analytical rigor and spatial precision (Borah et al., 2024). However, this type of model often overlooks the integration of local knowledge and community perception which are very important for contextualizing scientific findings and ensuring the relevance of risk information. Exclusion of community engagement may limit local understanding, empowerment and ownership in disaster risk management process. In contrast, incorporating participatory insights alongside the analytical technique not only strengthens the accuracy and social legitimacy of risk maps but also foster community engagement, shared responsibility and sustained resilience building process.

This study applies this integrative framework in Maidipur, Kurigram one of the most flood-prone areas in northern Bangladesh where recurrent monsoon floods cause severe social and economic disruption (Kabir Uddin, 2021; Mokhtari, 2023). Rooted in the Sendai Framework's Priority 1, Understanding Disaster Risk, the research combines community-based data collection with AHP and GIS to identify and classify hazard-prone zones, optimize flood shelter locations, and design evacuation routes. Additional technologies, including remote sensing for satellite image analysis, geospatial database development, and machine learning for land classification (Dang Tuyet Minh, 2018; Ravichandra N, 2023), are employed to improve the accuracy and usability of outputs. By bridging participatory knowledge with advanced spatial analytics, this study aims to support risk-informed decision-making and strengthen community resilience to floods.

1.1. Purpose

The purpose of the Community Risk Map is to make it easier to identify and prioritize areas at risk of flooding. By combining information about the likelihood of floods and how vulnerable the population is, the map helps local community people to understand their vulnerabilities and risk as well as authorities plan better for flood response. It helps identify the best evacuation routes, assembling points where to set up temporary shelters, and where to focus resources. This map plays a key role in improving community dignity, safety and inclusiveness, ensuring that people are better prepared for flood responses, including sheltering

1.2. Objectives

- Collect community-based hazard and vulnerabilities insights from the field level PRA tolls exercise and extract hydrological, meteorological, and geological data from satellite images using remote sensing techniques.

- Apply the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) model to analyze and assign weights to identify and delineate the hazard prone areas to visualize zones of high low flood risk.
- Assess Exposure and Vulnerability household, infrastructure and livelihoods by integrating community perception with AHP-GIS based analysis to better understand risk dynamics and develop community risk maps that identify and categorize zones according to composite vulnerability and hazard Indices.
- Identify and map evacuation routes and safe assembly points to optimize travel times and accessibility for flood-affected population and response planning, thereby strengthening early warning, evacuation and repose planning to support timely action, evidence-based decision making, and effective resources allocation for community preparedness, and resilience

1.3. Study Area

The “Maidipur Government Primary School” is Primary School located in Kurigram Sadar Upazila (Sub-district) of Kurigram District. The catchment area of the Sub-project mostly comprises of Moidipara, Sabujpara, Mtherpar, Moddho Kumorpur, Bagher para villages which are the victims of the flood caused by the overflow of the Dharala River and heavy rainfall during monsoon. The population of the catchment area is about four thousand five hundred (approximately). Figure 1 show the 1.5km radius the community of Maidipur GPS cum proposed flood shelter.

2. Methodology

2.1. Criteria Selection

All of the factors for each criterion have chosen based on the literature review (Mokhtari, 2023) and the definitions of hazards (natural and uncontrollable physical phenomena) and vulnerabilities (degree of susceptibility and exposure to man-made hazards) that has utilized in this study.

Step 1: Data Collection & Indicator Preparation

- Collect field data and information using the Hazard Vulnerability and Capacity Assessment (HVCA) tools- Transect Walk, Hazard Historical Timeline, Seasonal Calendar, FGD and KII with community-based stakeholders and secondary data and satellite imagery.
- Prepare hazard and vulnerability indicators.

Step 2: Ranking & Weight Assignment Using AHP

- Rank indicators and assign weights with AHP
- Create two Indices:
 - Hazard Index: Areas prone to flooding
 - Vulnerability Index: Areas with higher vulnerability (population, infrastructure).

Step 3: Community Risk Map

- Combine Hazard and Vulnerability Indices using the formula:
 - Risk = Hazard Index × Vulnerability Index
- Identify evacuation routes and assembly points

Step 4: Map Validation

- Cross-check the community risk map for accuracy assessment by engaging community stakeholders.

Figure 2. Hierarchy of community risk map.

The Community Risk Map aims to identify the risk zone by collecting demographic data from the field, extracting Social Map, hydrological, meteorological, and geological data from satellite images using remote sensing techniques, developed Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) model in GIS to determine vulnerable and flood hazard index, creating categorized risk zone, and these maps help in planning evacuation routes, temporary shelters, and resource allocation. About 14 indicators have been analyzed to create community risk mapping.

2.2. Data Collection

The details of data collection are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Datasets and sources

Sl. No	Index	Data Name	Source
1	Hazard	Land Elevation Model (DEM)	SRTM-Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from USGS Server (https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/)
2		Land Slope	Derived from DEM using hydrology tools in ArcGIS.
3		Drainage Density	DEM-derived stream network using hydrology tools in ArcGIS.
4		Distance to River	Sketch or social map and Euclidean Distance measured in GIS.
5		Annual Rainfall	CHIRPS Annual Precipitation, 2024
6		Topographic Wetness Index (TWI)	GIS-based calculation using DEM.
7		Return Period Flood Inundation (10 yrs)	Historical Timeline and Remote Sensing technique on Google Earth Engine. (Sentinel-1&2, Satellite Image 2014-2024)
8		Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	Remote Sensing technique on Google Earth Engine. (Sentinel-2, Satellite Image 2024)
9		Soil Type	Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council.
10	Vulnerability	Population Density	Calculated from population data collected in the field survey transect walk of the HVCA process
11		Vulnerable Population	Age < 14, Age > 65, Person with Disability (PWD) & Woman
12		Land Use and Land Cover (LULC)	Machine Learning Model on Google Earth Engine. (Sentinel-2, Satellite Image 2024)
13		Distance to Hospital/Clinic	Report on transect walk and Euclidean Distance measured in GIS.
14		Distance to Road	Sketch or social map of Euclidean Distance measured in GIS.

2.3. Data Preparation

In this study, GIS and remote sensing techniques were used to prepare various spatial indicators for generating the flood risk map. Community-based social maps were first prepared through participatory sketch mapping in the field, then scanned, georeferenced, and digitized in ArcGIS to create spatial databases within a 1.5 km radius of flood shelters. The key indicators included Digital Elevation Model (DEM), slope, drainage density, distance to river, topographic wetness index (TWI), annual rainfall, flood inundation, NDVI, soil type, population density, vulnerable population, land use/land cover (LULC), distance to hospital, and distance to road. Data was collected from reliable sources such as USGS, BARC, CHIRPS/TRMM, and Sentinel-2 imagery, and processed using ArcGIS and Google Earth Engine. All raster layers were reclassified into five natural breaks (1–5) using the Reclassify tool based on hazard and vulnerability indices and finally integrated through the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to generate the composite risk map.

2.4. Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), developed by Saaty (1990), is a multi-criteria decision-making technique used to solve complex problems systematically. It is widely applied in spatial planning and risk assessment, especially when combined with GIS. In AHP, the relative importance (weight) of each criterion is determined using the pairwise comparison method (PCM) based on expert judgment (Generino P. Siddayao, 2014). A square $n \times n$ comparison matrix is created, where each element represents the importance of one factor over another (Daniela Rincon, 2018). The importance is rated on a 1–9 scale, where 1 indicates equal importance and 9 indicates that one factor is extremely more important than the other, following Saaty’s scale in Table 2.

Table 2. Saaty’s 1–9 scale for Analytical Hierarchy Process (Saaty, 1987).

Scale	Importance	Reciprocal
1	Equal importance	1
3	Moderate importance	1/3
5	Essential or strong importance	1/5
7	Very strong importance	1/7
9	Extreme importance	1/9
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values between the two factors	1/2, 1/4, 1/6, 1/8

To ensure reliability in the pairwise comparison matrix, a Consistency Ratio (CR) is calculated. It checks whether the judgments are consistent, and its value should be less than 0.1 for valid results. The ratio is defined by Equation (3).

$$CR = CI/RI, \tag{3}$$

The Consistency Index (CI) was calculated using Equation (4).

$$CI = (\lambda_{max} - n)/(n - 1), \tag{4}$$

where CI is the Consistency Index and RI is the Random Index (Saaty, Table 3) and λ is the average consistency vector and n is the number of factors.

Table 3. Random Inconsistency Indices for $n = 1, 2 \dots 10$.

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

If $CR \leq 0.1$ or $CR \leq 10\%$, the matrix is consistent and if it exceeds 10%, a revision is required (Nsangou, 2022).

2.5. Prioritization Matrix

The principle of development is the following matrix:

- Determine the eigenvectors (Vp) of each criterion for each item is described in the following equation:

$$Vp = \sqrt[n]{W1 \times \dots \times Wk} \tag{5}$$

With k = number of parameters and comparing Wk ratings to main parameters.

- Calculate the weighting coefficients (Cp), the formula is given in the following equation:

$$Cp = \frac{Vp}{Vp1 + Vp2 + \dots + Vpk} \tag{6}$$

The sum of C_p of all parameters of a matrix must be equal to 1:

- Determine the maximum eigen value (λ_{\max}) by the following equation:

$$(7) \quad \lambda = \frac{E}{K}$$

- Calculate the consistency index (CI) expressed by the following equation:

$$(8) \quad CI = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - k}{K - 1}$$

- Determine the CR using Equation (3). The AHP method does not require that judgments are consistent or transitive, indeed, (Saaty, 1987) has defined the value of the CR. In the case where the value of the consistency ratio is less than 10%, the judgment is consistent and when it exceeds 10%, the assessments may require some revisions:

$$(9) \quad CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

(RI) is the random index, the values are shown in Table 3.

2.6. Hazard Index

The hazard index quantifies the probability and intensity of flooding. It represents natural, physical phenomena such as stream overflow and hydroclimatic processes that can damage land and property. Key factors considered in hazard mapping include slope, drainage density, soil type, and rainfall, as intense rainfall often triggers flooding (Gowhar Meraj, 2015). The resulting hazard map identifies areas susceptible to floods and the spatial extent of potential exposure. Using the Saaty scale, weights are assigned to each factor to calculate the eigenvector (V_p) and weighting coefficient (C_p), as shown in Tables 4 and 5.

$$V_p = \sqrt[11]{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 8} = 4.42 \quad \text{and} \quad C_p = \frac{4.42}{13.72} = 0.32 \quad (9)$$

Table 4: Hazard matrix

Parameters	E	S	DD	DR	TWI	RPID	Rainfall	NDVI	ST	V_p	C_p
E	1	3	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	4.42	0.32
S	1/3	1	3	4	4	5	6	7	7	3.06	0.22
DD	1/4	1/3	1	1	3	4	5	6	6	1.78	0.13
DR	1/4	1/4	1	1	3	4	5	6	6	1.72	0.13
TWI	1/5	1/4	1/3	1/3	1	3	4	5	5	1.06	0.08
RPID	1/6	1/5	1/4	1/4	1/3	1	3	4	4	0.68	0.05
Rainfall	1/7	1/6	1/5	1/5	1/4	1/3	1	3	3	0.44	0.03
NDVI	1/8	1/7	1/6	1/6	1/5	1/4	1/3	1	1	0.27	0.02
ST	1/8	1/7	1/6	1/6	1/5	1/4	1/3	1	1	0.27	0.02
SUM	2.57	5.47	10.10	11.10	16.98	23.83	31.66	41.00	41.00		

Table 5: Normalization of hazard matrix

Parameters	E	S	DD	DR	TWI	RPID	Rainfall	NDVI	ST	SUM	[C]	[D] = [A]*[C]	[E] = [D]/[C]	λ_{max}	CI	CR
E	0.39	0.55	0.40	0.36	0.29	0.25	0.22	0.20	0.20	2.85	0.31	3.25	10.25	9.50	0.06	0.04
S	0.13	0.18	0.30	0.36	0.24	0.21	0.19	0.17	0.17	1.94	0.21	2.27	10.48			
DD	0.10	0.06	0.10	0.09	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.15	1.14	0.12	1.24	9.79			
DR	0.10	0.05	0.10	0.09	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.15	1.13	0.12	1.23	9.78			
TWI	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.74	0.08	0.75	9.16			
RPID	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.50	0.05	0.49	8.80			
Rainfall	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.07	0.07	0.33	0.03	0.32	8.73			
NDVI	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.18	0.02	0.19	9.25			
ST	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.18	0.02	0.19	9.25			
SUM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00							

Note: E, elevation; S, slope; DD, drainage density; DR, distance to river; TWI, topographic wetness index; RPID, Return Period Inundation; NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; ST, Soil Type.

The relative hazard map is obtained by the given formula:

$$(11) \quad \text{Hazard Index} = 0.32 \times E + 0.22 \times S + 0.13 \times DD + 0.13 \times DR + 0.08 \times TWI + 0.05 \times RPID + 0.03 \times \text{Rainfall} + 0.02 \times NDVI + 0.02 \times ST$$

The **Consistency Ratio (CR)** is calculated by dividing the **Consistency Index (CI)** by the **Random Index (RI)**, where the RI is a pre-determined value based on the size of the matrix. The CI itself is derived from the **maximum eigenvalue** (λ_{max}) of the comparison matrix, as shown by the formula $CI = (\lambda_{max} - n) / (n - 1)$, where n is the matrix size. A CR value less than 0.10 (or 10%) is typically required to consider the judgments in the comparison matrix, often used in methods like the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), as acceptably consistent and therefore reliable.

2.7. Vulnerability Index

Vulnerability indicates the potential impact of a natural hazard on people, assets, and socio-economic activities. Vulnerability expresses the level of foreseeable consequences of a natural phenomenon on issues (Peter W Glynn, 2001) and on the other hand is the most crucial component of risk in that it determines whether or not exposure to a hazard constitutes a risk. Flood vulnerability mapping assesses the degree of susceptibility and exposure of an area to flooding. In this study, vulnerability is measured using some criteria with weights assigned to each factor as shown in Tables 6 and 7.

Table 6. Vulnerability matrix

Parameters	PD	VP	LULC	DTH	DTR	Vp	Cp
PD	1	1	2	3	4	2.21	0.34
VP	1.00	1	2	3	4	2.21	0.34
LULC	0.50	0.50	1	2	3	1.11	0.17
DTH	0.33	0.33	0.50	1	2	0.57	0.10
DTR	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.50	1	0.32	0.05
SUM	3.08	3.08	5.83	9.50	14.00	6.43	1.00

Table 7. Normalization of vulnerability matrix

Parameters	PD	VP	LULC	DTH	DTR	SUM	[C]	[D] = [A]*[C]	[E] = [D]/[C]	λ max	CI	CR
PD	0.32	0.32	0.34	0.32	0.29	1.59	0.34	1.49	4.329	5.12	0.030	0.027
VP	0.32	0.32	0.34	0.32	0.29	1.59	0.34	1.49	4.329			
LULC	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.21	0.21	0.92	0.17	0.84	4.881			
DTHC	0.11	0.11	0.09	0.11	0.14	0.55	0.10	0.50	5.590			
DTR	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.34	0.05	0.32	6.479			
SUM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00		1.00		25.607			

Note: PD, population density; VP, vulnerable population; LULC, land use and land cover; DTHC, distance to hospital/clinic; DTR, distance to road.

The relative map of vulnerability of land to flood is obtained from the formula:

$$(12) \quad \text{Vulnerability Index} = 0.34 \times \text{PD} + 0.34 \times \text{VP} + 0.17 \times \text{LULC} + 0.10 \times \text{DTH} + 0.05 \times \text{DTR}$$

Here, PD = population density, VP = vulnerable population, LULC = land use/land cover, DTH = distance to hospital, and DTR = distance to road. The model shows $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 5.12$ and CI = 0.030, indicating good consistency, as a CR below 0.1 is considered acceptable for pairwise comparisons.

2.8. Risk

Community risk mapping is the product of combining two features: vulnerability and hazard (Yashon O. Ouma, 2014). This model is suitable for natural hazards and is given by the following equation:

$$(13) \quad \text{Vulnerability Index} = 0.34 \times \text{PD} + 0.34 \times \text{VP} + 0.17 \times \text{LULC} + 0.10 \times \text{DTH} + 0.05 \times \text{DTR}$$

In modern contexts, risk is multidimensional, encompassing safety, economic, environmental, and social aspects. Studies show that effective flood management relies on three main components: risk (R), hazard (H), and vulnerability (V). Although definitions of risk vary, they consistently build on the core concepts of hazard and vulnerability (Muhammad Masood, 2012).

2.9. Identify Evacuation Route

The planning involves three key elements:

- **Nearest Flood Shelter:** which provide elevated and safe refuge.
- **Assembly Points:** designated safe gathering areas outside high-risk zones
- **Evacuation Routes:** Predefined paths connect assembly points to shelters based on the shortest distance and travel time to avoid risk zones. In this study, evacuation occurs primarily on foot from assembly points to shelters (Seula Park, 2020), with an average walking speed of 1.5 m/s, varying by time group as shown in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Walking speed of different age groups during evacuation.

Age Group	≤10	20–40	>60
Walking speed (m/s)	1.349	1.505	1.402

A slope reduces evacuee speed during evacuation. The road network was divided into 100 m segments, and the average slope of each segment was calculated using the “Add Surface Information” tool in GIS. These slope values were then used to adjust evacuation speeds according to **Table 9**.

Table 9. Evacuation speed correction based on slope.

Slope	0–3	3–6	6–9	9–12	12–15	15–18	18–21
Speed value	100%	85%	70%	55%	45%	40%	35%

Walking speed decreases in flooded areas. In this study, high susceptibility zones were treated as flooded, with a maximum pedestrian depth of 0.55 m. (Seula Park, 2020). Considering these, the modified speed after considering the flood is calculated using Equation (14) (Hye-Kyoung Lee, 2019):

$$v \text{ (m/s)} = V - 0.011d \text{ (cm)}, \tag{14}$$

where v is the walking speed (m/s), d is water depth (cm), and $V = 1.5$ m/s is the average walking speed. Evacuation routes considered safe assembly points, nearest flood shelters, road networks, and walking speed adjusted for flood depth, slope, and age groups.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Preliminary Findings - Return Period Flood Inundation

The return period indicates how often floods of a certain magnitude may occur, helping communities assess flood risk. Using Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) methods, local knowledge was combined with historical flood events to estimate flood return intervals where long-term data was unavailable. (Chambers, 1994; Mercer et al., 2009). In this study, community knowledge, historical timelines, and seasonal calendars were combined with 10 years of Sentinel-2 imagery in Google Earth Engine. The NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index) identified flooded areas, with values above 0.2 indicating water. By combining water masks over time, a flood frequency map was created, showing areas from low (light blue) to high (dark blue) occurrence. This map helps identify flood-prone and waterlogged areas, while a time series of NDWI highlights changes in water coverage over the years. Figure 3. Below shows the prepared Return Period Flood Inundation map for the last 10 years.

Figure 3. Return Period Flood Inundation map

The map shows flood intensity and frequency in Maidipur GPS near the Dharla River, classified into five categories over 10 years: Flood Free (0), Low (1–3), Average (3–5), High (5–7), and Extremely High (>7). Central and eastern areas, including Maidipur, Hindupara, and Sobujpara, are mostly

flood-free or low-risk, while western and southern areas, such as Mathpara, Char Sadar Para, and Mollah Para, experience higher flood frequency, with some zones in high to extremely high-risk categories. Based on these findings, community members and local authorities can plan appropriate risk reduction measures.

1. Flood-Free and Low-Risk Areas (0–3 occurrences in 10 years)

Actions:

- Maintenance the existing critical infrastructure e.g., embankments, drainage systems that help keep them flood-free zones.
- Use these zones for critical infrastructure (e.g., schools, health centers, flood shelters).
- Include them as potential safe shelter zones or could be considered as assembling point during floods affecting other areas.

2. Moderate-Risk Areas (3–5 flood occurrences in 10 years)

Actions:

- Raise house plinths and elevate latrines.
- Improve existing drainage infrastructure to minimize waterlogging.
- Promote climate-resilient agriculture (e.g., short-duration or flood-tolerant crops).
- Conduct community-based early warning drills and planning.

3. High to Extremely High-Risk Areas (5+ floods in 10 years)

Actions:

- Identify and prepare emergency evacuation routes and transport arrangements.
- Construct elevated community shelters or flood shelters (multi-purpose if possible).
- Strengthen and maintain embankments and water control structures.
- Encourage livelihood diversification to reduce dependence on flood-prone farming.
- Develop contingency plans for the household and para levels.
- Implement seasonal relocation plans (temporary shifting of people, livestock, or assets).

4. Cross-Cutting Actions (For All Zones)

- Disaster preparedness training for local volunteers, schools, and DMC.
- Strengthening community-based disaster management committees (CBDMCs) and SMC
- Establish and regularly update community risk maps and resource inventories.
- Promote use of local early warning systems (megaphones, mobile alerts, flags).
- Integrate indigenous knowledge and coping practices with scientific strategies.
- Ensure social inclusion: special attention to women, elderly, persons with disabilities, and children in planning and response.

Table 10. Role of Local Government

Area	Actions
Planning	Integrate flood risk zones into Ward Disaster Management Plan (WDMP) and Union Disaster Management Plans (UDMPs)
Coordination	Convene regular meetings of disaster management committees (DMCs), SMC including community representatives
Infrastructure	Prioritize investments in roads, drainage, and safe shelters in flood-prone areas.
Funding	Mobilize resources from national government and NGOs to implement risk reduction measures.
Policy Support	Enforce building codes, zoning restrictions, and safe agriculture practices.

Vulnerable Population The study considers the marginalized or vulnerable population as persons with disabilities, elderly people, women, and ethnic groups who are disproportionately affected by the flood. Figure 4 below shows the percentage of vulnerable populations for the community of Maidipur GPS. The map highlights the percentage of the vulnerable population in different neighborhoods of Maidipur GPS, considering individuals aged below 14, above 65, persons with disabilities, and women. The highest proportion of vulnerable people is found in Maidipur (35%), followed by Mathpara (25%), Bhogdanga (20%), and Sobujpara (19%). Areas like Char Sadar Para (18%) and Hindupara (13%) also show significant vulnerable groups. Mollah Para (10%) and Hatkhola (5%) have relatively lower proportions.

Figure 4. Percentage of Vulnerable Populations map

The fourteen factors used in the study were each categorized into five classes depending on their range of values as shown in Figure 5. and 6. The AHP technique provided the relative importance of each factor based on PCMs and the weight of each factor. Using the weighted overlay of all causative factors in the GIS environment, the final community risk map has generated.

3.2. 3.2 Final Findings - Hazard Index

A historical timeline exercise was conducted with community members to identify disaster years, types, and impacts, which were then validated using satellite imagery and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). The results show that elevation has the highest influence on flood occurrence with a weight of 0.32, followed by rainfall (0.03), drainage density (0.13), distance to road (0.13), TWI (0.08), distance to river (0.05), NDVI (0.02), and soil type (0.02). The Consistency Ratio (CR) of 0.04 confirms that the factor weightings are consistent (CR < 0.1). Table 11 and Figure 7 show the percentage of areas affected by floods.

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of hazard Index

Figure 8. Diagram of flood hazard intensity.

Table 7. Area coverage of the hazard zones

Hazard Intensity	Acres
Very low	220.467
Low	467.663
Medium	492.363
High	364.644
Very High	196.936
Total	1745.05

The flood hazard map (Figure 8) shows the distribution of flood risk across the study area. High and very high hazard zones are mainly found in Mathpara, Char Sadarpara, Hindupara, Hatkhola, Maidipur, and Bhogdanga, likely due to low-lying terrain or proximity to flood-prone channels. Areas such as Botola Bazar, Mathpara Bazar, and the old bus stand surroundings are very low hazard zones, indicating lower risk. Sobujpara village falls in the medium hazard zone, reflecting moderate risk. Overall, about 28.21% of the area is medium hazard, 20.90% high hazard, and 11.29% very high hazard.

Figure 9. Spatial character of vulnerability index

3.3. Vulnerability Index

The flood vulnerability map (Figure 9 and Table 11) is based on the Flood Vulnerability Index (FVI) scores obtained by indicator ranking and the AHP also incorporates five vulnerability classes ranging from Risk Free to very high levels of flood vulnerability. Unlike the Flood Hazard Index (FHI) scores, which mainly considered physical elements, this FVI analysis mainly takes into consideration demographic and socio-economic criteria.

Table 11. Area coverage of the flood Vulnerability zones

Vulnerability	Acres
Very low	160.752
Low	323.062
Medium	674.03
High	167.759
Very High	418.996
Total	1745.05

Figure 10. Diagram of flood vulnerability.

The vulnerability diagram (Figure 10) shows how different areas are susceptible to hazards. Very high vulnerability zones are mainly in Mathpara and Maidipur, indicating higher risk. Mollahpara and Hatkhola are low-risk areas. Medium vulnerability zones are seen in Bhogdanga, Hindupara, and Sobujpara. Overall, 38.63% of the area falls under medium vulnerability, while 24.01% is classified as very high vulnerability.

3.4. Community Risk Mapping

The community risk mapping thus generated is shown in Figure 11, in which the study is mainly divided into five classes based on flood potentiality: (1) Risk Free, (2) Low Risk, (3) Medium Risk, (4) Risk, and (5) High Risk Zone. The area's coverage and percentage are shown below.

Figure 11. Distribution of community risk mapping

Table 12. Area coverage of the risk zones

Risk Categories	Area in Acres	Number of Affected Buildings
Risk Free	282.892	803
Low Risk	511.834	1778
Medium Risk	510.014	636
Risk	285.489	455
High Risk	151.532	41
Total	1745.05	3713

Figure 12. Diagram of Risk Status

The community risk assessment (Table 12 & Figure 12) shows the distribution of flood risk across the study area. Very high-risk zones are mainly in Maidipur and Mathpara, covering 324.43 acres, with high population densities (2200 and 700 people/sq km) and a significant proportion of vulnerable people (35% and 25%). These areas lack nearby health facilities, have poor road connectivity, low-lying terrain, saturated soil, and ineffective drainage, making them highly susceptible to flooding.

High-risk zones are also observed in parts of Maidipur, Mathpara, and Char Sardarpara, while medium-risk zones cover Bhogdanga, Hindupara, Sobujpara, and parts of Mathpara. Low-risk zones include portions of Bhogdanga, Hindupara, Sobujpara, and Char Sardarpara, and risk-free areas are mainly in Hatkhola, Mollahpara, and parts of Hindupara, with stable soil, good drainage, low population density, and proximity to health services, covering 58.64, 118.21, and 100.60 acres, respectively.

Overall, the risk map, based on 14 key indicators, highlights areas needing targeted risk mitigation and preparedness, particularly for 455 buildings in risk areas and 41 buildings in high-risk zones. Flood-free and low-risk zones benefit from natural drainage into the Dead and Dharla Rivers, reducing waterlogging and ensuring minimal disruption.

The overall finding of the study will provide valuable insights for Local Government Institutions (LGIs), particularly the local-level Disaster Management Committee, to enhance evidence-based planning and implementation of development and humanitarian assistance program. Furthermore, the results will inform LGED's strategic approach to infrastructure development, contributing to inclusive growth, poverty reduction and community resilience through the improvement of local infrastructure and governance system.

3.5. Evacuation Route Plan

This system identifies 15 assembly points (temporary shelter) that are low-risk zones with 1.5 km radius, the community of Maidipur GPS has proposed flood shelter. This evacuation route has been planned to help people quickly and safely reach the shelter during floods, with the shortest time possible and shortest distance considering the impact of the flood on the speed of evacuees using closest service area analysis. Figure 11 shows the Evacuation route identification map.

3.6. 3.6 Limitation

This study has several limitations that need to be acknowledged. The population-related data, such as household numbers, total population, and vulnerable groups (children, elderly, women, and persons with disabilities), were collected tentatively from community sources rather than through a detailed field survey. A comprehensive survey would provide more accurate results but require additional cost and time. Collecting information from local community members was also challenging and time-consuming. For this assessment, a small group of participants were involved preparing one community risk map, but a larger effort would be needed for multiple communities. Moreover, the analysis used 2024 satellite imagery, as 2025 data were not fully available during the study period, which may have slightly affected data accuracy.

4. Accuracy assessment

A site visit was conducted to assess the accuracy of the community risk map developed for Kamalpur Government Primary School, located in Saghata Upazila, Gaibandha District. This site was chosen as a representative sample to evaluate the reliability and precision of the map's risk assessment data. The initial map was prepared at the head office in Dhaka, using both secondary and primary data. The map will be finalized dependent on field verification and consultation with local community people.

4.1. Validation Process

A participatory approach was adopted to gather local insights:

Community Engagement: Engaging with the schoolteachers and local community members to discuss the historical flood events and to identify vulnerable areas. These discussions highlighted critical infrastructure such as roads that were frequently affected during floods.

4.2. Field Observations

Field visits were conducted systematically to gather ground-truth data:

- **Team Composition:** The field validation team included three local people and a GIS expert with expertise in flood mapping.
- **Data Collection Points:** Hard copy and smart devices were used to collect data from 32 pre-identified points, ensuring spatial coverage.
- **Data Parameters:** Observations included water depth during floods, duration of inundation, land elevation, damage to infrastructure, road condition and usage patterns (e.g., agriculture or temporary shelters).

To further validate the community risk map, a local person with knowledge of the area was hired, and a team with a GIS expert visited the community by auto. This field visit covered a radius of 1.5 km from Maidipur GPS cum proposed flood shelter. In total, 32 key points were visited, and discussions were held with local people, followed by direct observations of the sites.

4.3. Key Findings

High-Risk Areas

- Locations: Madipur and Mathpara areas are among the most vulnerable.

Salient Features of the High-Risk Zone

1. **Geographical Exposure:** Settlements are located outside protective embankments and along the Dharla River, making them highly vulnerable to flooding and erosion.
2. **Severe and Prolonged Flooding:** Floodwaters rise to 7–8 feet and remain stagnant for 10–15 days, significantly disrupting daily life, agriculture, and infrastructure.
3. **River Erosion-Induced Displacement:** Continuous riverbank erosion forces families to relocate, contributing to social and economic instability.
4. **Inadequate Infrastructure:**
 - Absence of drainage systems leads to water stagnation.
 - Roads are unpaved, low-lying, and impassable during floods.
 - No flood shelters exist; people rely on informal shelters such as embankments or relatives' homes.
5. **Limited Access to Essential Services:**
 - Healthcare facilities collapse during disasters.
 - No nearby markets or veterinary services are available, affecting access to food and animal care.
6. **Weak Emergency Preparedness and Response:**
 - No early warning system exists for floods.
 - There is a lack of trained rescue personnel and emergency assistance mechanisms.
7. **Livelihood and Food Insecurity:** Crop damage due to flooding results in food shortages, affecting both human and livestock well-being.

Risk Free Areas

- **Locations:** Elevated regions in Hatkhola, Mollahpara and parts of Hindupara experienced minimal or no flooding.
- **Community Use:** Embankment (near shelter) was identified as a high land area used by the community as a temporary shelter during floods. The fact that this area has not been recorded in previous flood events may indicate it is usually safe from flooding, possibly due to its higher elevation or natural barriers in the surrounding landscape.

Salient Features of the Risk-Free Zone

1. **Lower Flood Exposure:** The area experiences relatively lower flood levels compared to high-risk zones.
2. **Protected Location:** Homesteads are situated within the WAPDA embankment, offering protection against floodwater.

3. Higher Elevation and Strong Infrastructure: Settlements are located on elevated ground with strong, well-built houses and paved roads that ensure year-round accessibility.
4. Functional Drainage System: Effective drainage infrastructure prevents water stagnation and reduces flood impact.
5. Distance from River: The area is far from the riverbank, minimizing direct exposure to flood-water.
6. Continuous Access to Health Services: Health facilities are available within the area and remain operational during floods or other disasters.
7. No Need for Evacuation: Residents do not require relocation or sheltering during flood events due to the area's inherent safety.
8. Market Accessibility: Daily necessities remain accessible during floods, with functional markets located nearby.
9. Reliable Civic Amenities: The zone benefits from higher availability of citizen services, including transportation, healthcare, and infrastructure.
10. Community Use of Elevated Areas: Embankments near shelters serve as communal high-ground refuge points, when necessary, although such needs are rare due to the area's flood resilience.

4.4. Validation Results

Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics

A confusion matrix was constructed to evaluate the model's performance:

Predicted \ Actual zoning	Risk zone delineation presented in the mapped output	Findings from field observations				
		Risk Free	Low Risk	Medium Risk	Risk	High Risk
Risk Free	6	5	1	0	0	0
Low Risk	8	0	8	0	0	0
Medium Risk	5	0	0	5	0	0
Risk	4	0	0	0	4	0
High Risk	9	0	0	0	0	9

4.5. Key Metrics:

- **Overall Accuracy:**

$$\text{Accuracy} = \text{Correct Predictions} / \text{Total Predictions} = 31/32 \times 100 = 96.88\%$$

- **Precision (High Risk):**

$$\text{Precision} = \text{True Positives (High)} / (\text{True Positives (High)} + \text{False Positives (High)}) = 4 / (4+0) \times 100 = 100\%$$

- **Recall (High Risk):**

$$\text{Recall} = \text{True Positives (High)} / (\text{True Positives (High)} + \text{False Negatives (High)}) = 4 / (4+0) \times 100 = 100\%$$

- **F1 Score (High Risk):**

$$F1 = 2 \times (\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}) = 100\%$$

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of combining local knowledge with scientific analysis using AHP and GIS to assess and map community flood risk in a hazard-prone, data-scarce region of northern Bangladesh. The framework used 14 indicators covering both physical hazards and social vulnerabilities. Weighted overlay analysis with AHP produced hazard and vulnerability indices, which were combined into a composite flood risk map. High-risk areas were concentrated in Maidipur and Mathpara, due to low elevation, poor drainage, dense population, and limited access to services, while Hatkhola and Mollahpara showed minimal risk because of better topography and infrastructure.

Evacuation planning, adjusted for flood-affected walking speeds, identified practical routes and assembly points within a 1.5 km buffer of the proposed flood shelter. Field validation through transects walks, participatory assessments, and site observations confirmed a high model accuracy of 96.88%, highlighting the robustness of the approach. Overall, the study underscores AHP-GIS as a replicable and context-appropriate method for local-level flood risk assessment and preparedness planning in vulnerable regions.

As the study adopts an inclusive approach and integrates local knowledge with evidence-based method, it ensures a high level of accuracy and contextual relevance. Therefore, the approach and findings have strong potential for replication in other flood-prone regions within Bangladesh and in similar context abroad.

5.1. Recommendations

- **Risk-informed Local Development Planning:** The flood risk maps generated through this study should be mainstreamed into local development and disaster management plans. Priority should be given to high-risk zones (e.g., Maidipur and Mathpara) for infrastructure investments, such as flood-resilient roads, drainage upgrades, and household elevation programs.
- **Operationalization of Evacuation Plans:** Identified evacuation routes and assembly points should be formally recognized, maintained, and communicated through community signage and early warning dissemination systems. Their design must account for variable evacuation speeds due to age, terrain, and flood depth.
- **Institutionalizing Community Risk Mapping:** Periodic updates of the community risk map should be institutionalized through participatory mechanisms involving Union Disaster Management Committees (UDMCs), ensuring that emerging hazards and community perceptions are regularly captured and integrated.
- **Replication Across the Disaster Risk Management project Areas:** Given the model's success, the AHP-GIS framework should be scaled to other vulnerable sub-project areas under any Disaster Risk Reduction project, enabling a harmonized approach to flood risk assessment.
- **Enhancing Data Ecosystem for Real-time Decision Support:** Establish linkages with meteorological and hydrological data platforms to support real-time flood monitoring and early warning systems, enabling dynamic risk mapping and anticipatory action.
- **Strengthening Local Preparedness and Capacity:** Local disaster responders and community members should be trained in interpreting and using risk maps for preparedness, evacuation, and recovery planning, further embedding risk awareness into community resilience processes.

6. Reference

1. Abdel Rahman Al-Shabeeb, R. A.-A. (2016). AHP with GIS for a preliminary site selection of wind turbines in the Northwest of Jordan. *International Journal of Geosciences*, 7(10), 1208–1221. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ijg.2016.710090>
2. Abdulla-Al Kafy, A.-A.-F. M. (2020). Impact of LULC changes on LST in Rajshahi District of Bangladesh: A remote sensing approach. *Journal of Geographical Studies*, 3(1), 11–23. <https://doi.org/10.21523/gcj5.19030102>
3. Abhishek Banerjee, R. C. (2020). An analysis of long-term rainfall trends and variability in the Uttarakhand Himalaya using Google Earth Engine. *Remote Sensing*, 12(4), 709. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12040709>
4. Borah, P. B., Das, S., & Hazarika, R. (2024). *Flood risk assessment utilizing GIS-based AHP and MCDM approaches integrating local knowledge and community perception*. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-024-07100-3>
5. Chambers, R. (1994). Participatory rural appraisal (PRA): Analysis of experience. *World Development*, 22(9), 1253–1268.
6. Dang Tuyet Minh, N. B. (2018). Application of GIS technology to establish a drainage density hierarchical map for flood hazard zoning in Lam river basin. *Journal of Mining and Earth Sciences*, 59(6), 32–42. Retrieved from <https://tapchi.humg.edu.vn/en/archives?article=1068>
7. Daniela Rincon, U. T. (2018). Flood risk mapping using GIS and multi-criteria analysis: A Greater Toronto Area case study. *Geosciences*, 8(8), 275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences8080275>
8. Diego Alonso Arias-Choquehuanca, B. I.-N.-J. (2023). Flooding mapping detection and urban affectation using Google Earth Engine. *Dyna*, 90(229), 129–136. <https://doi.org/10.15446/dyna.v90n229.109296>
9. Elhadj Mokhtari, F. M. (2023). Flood risk assessment using analytical hierarchy process: A case study from the Cheliff-Ghrib watershed, Algeria. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 14(3), 694–711. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wcc.2023.316>
10. Ethiopia Bisrat, B. B. (2018). Identification of surface water storing sites using topographic wetness index (TWI) and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). *Journal of Natural Resources and Development*, 8, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.5027/jnrd.v8i0.09>
11. Generino P. Siddayao, S. E. (2014). Analytic hierarchy process (AHP) in spatial modeling for floodplain risk assessment. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing*, 4(5), 2010–3700. <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJMLC.2014.V4.453>
12. Gowhar Meraj, S. A. (2015). Assessing the influence of watershed characteristics on the flood vulnerability of Jhelum basin in Kashmir Himalaya. *Natural Hazards*, 77(13), 153–175. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-015-1605-1>
13. Hye-Kyoung Lee, W.-H. H.-H. (2019). Experimental study on the influence of water depth on the evacuation speed of elderly people in flood conditions. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 39, 101198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101198>
14. Kabir Uddin, M. A. (2021). Potential flood hazard zonation and flood shelter suitability mapping for disaster risk mitigation in Bangladesh using geospatial technology. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 11, 100185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2021.100185>
15. Melkamu Alebachew Anley, A. S. (2022). Assessing the impacts of land use/cover changes on ecosystem service values in Rib watershed, Upper Blue Nile Basin, Ethiopia. *Trees, Forests and People*, 7, 100212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tfp.2022.100212>
16. Muhammad Masood, K. T. (2012). Assessment of flood hazard, vulnerability and risk of mid-eastern Dhaka using DEM and 1D hydrodynamic model. *Natural Hazards*, 12, 757–770. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-011-0060-x>
17. Nsangou, D. (2022). Urban flood susceptibility modelling using AHP and GIS approach: Case of the Mfoundi watershed at Yaoundé in the South-Cameroon plateau. *Scientific African*, 15, 1043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2021.e01043>

18. Peter W Glynn, J. M. (2001). Coral bleaching and mortality in Panama and Ecuador during the 1997–1998 El Niño–Southern Oscillation event: Spatial/temporal patterns and comparisons with the 1982–1983 event. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 79, 79–109. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233572646>
19. Ravichandra N, Y. P. (2023). Change detection of NDVI in Sangareddy district using Google Earth Engine (GEE). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 12(11), 2189–2195. Retrieved from <https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/?year=2023&vol=12&issue=11&ArticleId=24334>
20. Robert C. Weih Jr, T. L. (2004). Modeling slope in a geographic information system. *Journal of the Arkansas Academy of Science*, 58, 18. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.uark.edu/jaas/vol58/iss1/18>
21. Saaty, R. (1987). The analytic hierarchy process—What it is and how it is used. *Mathematical Modelling*, 9(3–5), 161–176. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0270-0255\(87\)90473-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0270-0255(87)90473-8)
22. Seula Park, G. L. (2020). Flood evacuation mapping using a time–distance cartogram. *International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(4), 207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9040207>
23. Yashon O. Ouma, R. T. (2014). Urban flood vulnerability and risk mapping using integrated multi-parametric AHP and GIS: Methodological overview and case study assessment. *Water*, 6(6), 1515–1545. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w6061515>

